

GENETIC DIVERSITY OF *FUSARIUM ANNULATUM* FROM MARATHWADA REGION (MS)

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ABSTRACT

The Marathwada region in Maharashtra, known for its agricultural crop production the major cultivated crop is pulses, oilseed and cash crop. *Fusarium* wilt is serious fungal disease, which causes huge yield losses in Agriculture crop. *Fusarium* is large and diverse genus of imperfect fungi. During the study of genetic diversity of *Fusarium annulatum*, infected samples were collected from different environmental conditions in Kharif- 2022-2023. It was found that the different isolates from different localities were shows the morphological as well as genetic diversity among each other. The genetic variability in the *Fusarium annulatum* isolates may be due to difference in geographical and environmental conditions. The ITS primer analysis found diversity among *Fusarium annulatum* isolates at molecular characterization. The High-level variability seen in FOM-01 to FOM-08, and relationship with cultural and pathogenic traits. The cluster analysis of ITS primer group of eight FOM.

Keywords: Agricultural, Wilt, *Fusarium*, Genetic diversity, ITS, FOM.

INTRODUCTION

The Genera *Fusarium* is important pathogenic genera associated with different plants, crops, fruit plants, vegetables crops, etc. *Fusarium* species causing disease like wilts, blights, root-rots and cankers in crop plants. *Fusarium* spp. produces many types of mycotoxins which are harmful to plant as well human health. *Fusarium* is a large diverse genus of imperfect fungi and important plant pathogenic species (Nelson, et. al., 1981). *Fusarium* have complex, heterogeneous, and large genus which restricts diverse taxa with varying morphological, physiological, and ecological characteristics (Vujanovic, et. al., 2006). The fungus is introduced by Link in 1809 which having ability to spore-producing filamentous ascomycete. The occurrence of *Fusarium* shows the abundance in the soil, it is considered to be soilborne. Usually found *Fusarium* associated as a parasite or saprophyte, the fungus is known to destroy a wide variety of important agricultural crops which are economically very important.

Fusarium usually also causes diseases to horticultural crops, ornamental crops, and in both natural and agricultural ecosystems. It not only causes diseases but also contaminates agricultural products, foods, fruits and food grains by releasing secondary metabolites, commonly known as mycotoxins and thus threatening the food security (Yadav, et. al., 2020). Along with these *Fusarium* were able to synthesize phytotoxins and mycotoxins as secondary metabolites, which can play an important role in the pathogenesis (Lombard, 2019 and Summerell, 2019).

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Some *Fusarium* species are considered to be hemibiotrophs capable of switching to necrotrophs depending on the host and environmental conditions (Summerell, 2019 and Rampersad, 2020; Gujjeti et al., 2014). Furthermore, it has been difficult to distinguish closely related *Fusarium* species, due to inter-/intra-species overlap and inconsistency in morphological traits. By applying a polyphasic taxonomic approach that combines morphological observations with DNA fingerprinting, and multilocus phylogenetic analysis (MLSA), many species have been described *Fusarium spp.* complex, prominent to noteworthy development in the *Fusarium* classification system (Crous, et. al., 2021, Lombard, 2019, Yilmaz, et. al., 2021, McTaggart, et. al., 2021 and Bedoya, et. al., 2021; Gujjeti et al., 2013). *Fusarium* research over the past 100 years has advanced our understanding of this important group of fungi, many aspects of its biology still need to study. The genus *Fusarium* includes a very wide range of genetically diverse species which can further evolve based on changing environment and management practices. Recently, efficient tools have been developed which help in studying the dynamics and diversity of a genetically diverse organism under study. One of those tools is (inter-simple sequence repeats) ISSR marker which helped in quantification of the diversity present in the genus (Akbar, et. al., 2018).

Agriculture is backbone of the Indian economy mainly based on and more than 70% of total population depends. Production of sufficient quantity of food, which can feed the whole population of country has always been a great challenge. Various environmental challenges such as storms, droughts, flood, etc. contribute a major portion of crop yield loss in agriculture (Iizumi and Ramankutty, 2015). Apart from these, loss in agricultural production continues to be constrained by a number of biotic and abiotic factors (Rai and Ingle, 2012). The important biotic factors affecting agricultural production mostly include soil fungi, insects-pests, parasites and predators. Among them fungal incidence major problem associated with these crops and more predominant attack of *Fusarium*, which causes tremendous loss in Indian economy (Ingle, et. al., 2008). The diversity of *Fusarium annulatum* were analysed phylogenetic based on ITS sequences showed the presence of at evolutionary lineages of the pathogen from Marathwada region from different crops like

vegetables, pulses, fruit and soil, it was found that abundance occurrence with diversity were seen.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The present work was carried out at the Seed Pathology and Fungal Biotechnology Laboratory, Department of Botany, Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar Marathwada University, Chhatrapati Sambhajnagar, during the year of 2022-2023. The details of field and laboratory procedure followed during this research work are described in this chapter.

Collection of Wilted Samples

The wilt affected samples were collected from different localities of Marathwada region such as Chhatrapati Sambhajnagar, Jalna and Parbhani. The wilt affected sample are collected in early morning in a sterilized paper bag or zip lock polythene bag, each wilted samples locality takes the GPS camera photograph and polythene bag was labeled properly by in the locality of collection, date and time (Figure 1). Then the collected sample were taken to the laboratory and these wilted samples were preserved at 4°C in refrigerator and used for further studies.

Sterilization of Sample

The infected sample were surface sterilized with 0.1% Mercuric Chloride (HgCl₂) for 30 sec. and washed 3-4 times with sterilized double distilled water to remove traces of HgCl₂. The surface sterilized samples were then placed on Potato Dextrose Agar Media (PDA) and Czapek Dox Agar (CZA) medium containing streptomycin (0.12gm/lit.) and incubated at 30°C for 5-6 days.

Isolation of the *Fusarium annulatum*

Fusarium annulatum were major isolated from roots, stem and wilted plants of different crops. From this isolation Eight FOM of *Fusarium annulatum*, were obtained. Growth of fungus was observed 5-7 days after incubation at 27°C in all FOM isolates.

Purification of *Fusarium annulatum* isolates

All the isolates of the pathogen were purified by single spore isolation method (Hansen, H. N., 1926) Sufficient care was taken to maintain the purity of the isolates throughout the study.

Figure 1. Collection of *Fusarium* Wilted crop sample from different region of Marathwada

Selection of Media for Isolation

1] Potato Dextrose Agar (PDA) (Rangaswami, 1972)

Peeled Potato – 200g, Dextrose – 20g, Agar-Agar – 20g, Streptomycin – 0.2g, Distilled Water (D/W) – 1000ml, pH -5.5 to 5.6

2] Czapek Dox Agar (CZA)

Sucrose – 30g, Sodium Nitrate (NaNO_3) – 2.0g, Potassium Dihydrogen Phosphate (KH_2PO_4) – 1.0g, Magnesium Sulphate Heptahydrate ($\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$) – 0.5g, Potassium Chloride (KCl) – 0.5g, Ferrous

Sulphate Heptahydrate ($\text{FeSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$) – 0.01g, Agar-Agar – 20g and Distilled Water (D/W) – 1000ml, pH – 5.5 to 5.6

Microscopic Identification Fusarium species

After the growth of *Fusarium* on the petri plates. The Macroscopic observation was done by external feature, texture, colony color, growth rate and microscopic characteristics are arrangement of conidia. Macroscopic and Microscopic features of

Fusarium fungi are helpful in the accurate identification of *Fusarium* fungi. The identification of *Fusarium* Fungi was done by using the various research paper, monographs and other literature such as Manual of soil fungi (Joseph, C., Gilman, J.C., 1998), Handbook of soil Fungi (Nagamani, A., et. al., 2006), *Fusarium* Species: An Illustrated Manual for

Identification (Nelson, P.E., et. al., 1983; Vijayagiri et al., 2012), The *Fusarium* Laboratory Manual (Leslie, J.F., Summerell, B.A., 2006), Fuskey: *Fusarium* Interactive Key (Seifert, K., 1996), The Illustration of Fungi (Mukadam, D. S., 2006).

Morphological Characterization

To study Morphology of Macroconidia, Microconidia and Chlamyospore 7-9-day old culture of each isolate grown on PDA medium was stained with 0.1% Lactophenol cotton blue on slide and observed under compound microscope.

Growth pattern and Morphological Characteristics of *Fusarium* species

In order to study growth pattern and Morphological characteristics of *Fusarium annulatum* isolates which are isolated from different wilted agriculture crop, were grown on solid Potato Dextrose Agar (PDA) Medium. These isolates were incubated room temperature at 30°C for 7-9 days on Potato Dextrose Agar (PDA) Medium and the result were in the form of colony color, colony pattern and colony diameter. The study of Morphology of Macroconidia, Microconidia and Chlamyospore 7-9 days old culture of each isolate grown on PDA medium was stained with 0.1% Lactophenol cotton blue on slide and observed under compound Microscope.

Genetic Variability

Internal transcribed spacer (ITS) is the spacer was used to detect the variation among the isolates of *Fusarium annulatum*. Standardized protocol was used for the isolation of DNA and analysis.

DNA isolation

The standardized protocol of Cenis (1992) for DNA extraction was used with some modifications and yielded was amenable to PCR amplification.

Extraction and Purification of Genomic DNA

One week old mycelial mat was filtered through Whatman No.1 filter paper and air dried. Around 0.1 g of Mycelium was placed in a mortar and homogenized with 1 ml of extraction buffer and the homogenate was transferred to a 2 ml-microfuge tube. An equal volume of Phenol: Chloroform: Isoamylalcohol (25:24:1) was added to the tubes and mixed well by gently shaking the tubes. The tubes were centrifuged at room temperature for 15 min at 14,000 rpm. The upper aqueous phase was collected in a new tube and an equal volume of Chloroform: Isoamyl alcohol (24:1) was added and mixed. The upper aqueous phase obtained after centrifuging at room temperature for 10 min at 14,000 rpm was transferred to a new tube. The DNA was precipitated from the solution by adding 0.1 volume of 3 M Sodium acetate pH 7.0 and 0.7 volume of Isopropanol. After 15 min of incubation at room temperature the tubes were centrifuged at 4°C for 15 min at 14,000 rpm. The DNA pellet was washed twice with 70% ethanol and then very briefly with 100% ethanol and air dried. The DNA was dissolved in TE (Tris-Cl 10 mM pH 8.0, EDTA 1 mM). To remove RNA 5 µl of DNase free RNase (10 mg/ml) was added to the DNA.

Dilution of DNA Samples

A part of DNA sample was diluted with appropriate quantity of sterilized double distilled water to yield a working concentration of 155 ng of Extracted DNA is used for amplification along with 10pM of each primer and stored at 4°C.

DNA Fingerprinting profile

The ITS-PCR protocol was used with some modification to produce DNA fingerprinting profile to produce 8 fungal isolates of *Fusarium annulatum*. The PCR amplification reaction was optimized by varying concentration of PCR component. Amplification reaction was carried out in 50 µl reaction mixtures containing 155ng of fungal genomic DNA, 10X PCR buffer, 3.2 mM MgCl₂ 0.5 mM dNTPs, 10pM primers and 3U of Taq DNA polymerase. PCR amplification was performed in master cycler gradient, Eppendorf PCR thermocycler, and the program consisted of an initial denaturing at 94°C for 3 min, followed by 30 cycles comprising denaturation at 94°C for 1 min, annealing at 50°C and extension of 2 min. at 72°C. The final extension was set at 72°C for 7 min. PCR amplified product was separated by electrophoresis on 1.5%

agarose gel in 10X TAE buffer, stained with Ethidium bromide and visualized under gel documentation system.

ITS Analysis

The Primer ITS were screened which showed clear difference in sequence, which are used for genetic diversity analysis of 8 FOM isolates. The PCR reaction was set in a 50ul reaction volume.

PCR Reaction

Master mix was prepared with the above-mentioned reagents and divided into 8 equal parts (each of 50 ul) into 8 different PCR tubes 1ul of 8 different genomic DNA samples of Fungal isolates was added to master mix by changing tips to avoid contamination that leads to final quantity of 50 ul. PCR tubes were then placed in thermal cycler for amplification of the genomic DNA as per the standardized protocol by modification by Williams, et. al., (1990) with some modifications according to selected primer.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The result of the present study entitled “Genetic diversity of *Fusarium annulatum* from Marathwada region of Maharashtra states”, we have collected different wilted plants, stem, roots, soil and plant debris from 03 different district of Marathwada like, Jalna, Chhatrapati Sambhajnagar and Parbhani. On different crop sample are isolated 138 isolates from these *Fusarium annulatum* show the major diversity in their FOM (Table 1). It was seen that 08 different FOM (Figure 2,3,4) were isolated from major crops of Marathwada regions like as, Pigeon pea, Chickpea, Brinjal, Bottle gourd, Sugarcane, Cotton, Niger crop and Custard apple. Studied the 08 isolates belonging

to different species of *Fusarium annulatum* were subjected to amplification by ITS primer. The data obtained from ITS primer clearly distinguished the isolates of fungus used for study of genetic relationships. The primer method differentiated clusters within species. The result obtained in the study are presented under following heading.

Morphology of *Fusarium annulatum*

Fusarium annulatum culture had characteristic violet pigmentation on PDA. On the sides, the colour was deep purple. In general, the aerial mycelium had a cottony, Fluffy appearance, was initially white but gradually turned violet as it aged, and becoming grey in some areas but in FOM no. 01, 05 and 08 showing whitish pink and in FOM no. 02, 03 and 07 mycelium shows whitish colour, FOM no. 04 show whitish cream colour mycelium. The different FOM of *Fusarium annulatum* shown difference in colony diameter. The highest growth was observed in FOM no. 06 (3.6cm) but FOM no. 02 shows lowest growth (2.3cm). Deep purple sporodochia were occasionally observed. The scant macroconidia had straight, thin, partitioned arrangements (3–4 septa). Macroconidium sizes ranged from 20 to 55 µm length and from 3.7 to 5 µm width; the macroconidium apical cells were blunt, and the basal cells were foot-shaped. The abundant microconidia were observed in long chains supported by monophialides and polyphialides. No septa were detected in the microconidia, their shapes varied from obovoid or nearly oval with a truncate bases, to fusiform, while they ranged from 5.2 to 13.5 × 2.5 to 3.2 µm. No chlamydospores were observed (Table No. 02).

DNA Extraction

Genomic DNA of Eight *Fusarium annulatum* isolates was extracted from their mycelial mat grown

Table 1. Isolates of *Fusarium annulatum* Collected from Different regions of Marathwada

Sr. No.	Isolates Codes	Isolate Source	District	Tahshil
FOM-1	M	Pigeon Pea	Jalna	Partur
FOM-2	MGF30	Chickpea	Chh. Sambhajnagar	Khultabad
FOM-3	F53	Brinjal	Jalna	Mantha
FOM-4	F71	Bottle Gourd	Jalna	Badnapur
FOM-5	F46	Sugarcane	Jalna	Ghansavangi
FOM-6	F67	Cotton	Parbhani	Gangakhed
FOM-7	F02	Niger Crop	Chh. Sambhajnagar	Paithan
FOM-8	F23	Custard Apple	Jalna	Ambad

Figure 2. Pure Culture and Microscopic photograph of *Fusarium annulatum*

Figure 3. Pure Culture and Microscopic Photograph of *Fusarium annulatum*

Figure 4. Pure Culture and Microscopic Photograph of *Fusarium annulatum*

Table 2. Morphological, Cultural and Microscopic Characteristics of 08 different *Fusarium annulatum*

Sr. No.	<i>Fusarium annulatum</i> Code	Front colony Colour	Reverse Colony Colour	Colony Diameter (Cm)	Type of Mycelium
1	FOM-1	Whitish Pink	Pinkish Purple	2.8	Irregular, Cottony Aerial Mycelium
2	FOM-2	Whitish	Creamish	2.3	Compact, Rounded Aerial Mycelium
3	FOM-3	Whitish	Creamish	2.6	Rounded, Cottony Aerial Mycelium
4	FOM-4	Whitish Cream	Off-white	2.6	Irregular, Fluffy Aerial Mycelium
5	FOM-5	Whitish Pink	Cream	2.8	Compact, Fluffy Aerial Mycelium
6	FOM-6	Pinkish White	Purplish	3.6	Fluffy, Cottony Aerial Mycelium
7	FOM-7	Whitish	Off-white	3.3	Rounded, Cottony Aerial Mycelium
8	FOM-8	Whitish Pink	Purplish Pink	3.1	Irregular, Fluffy Aerial Mycelium

Note: Diameter of colony after 7 days of growth at 30°C

on potato dextrose agar by using protocol of Cenis (1992) with some modification and yielded 350-400ng/μl quantity of DNA which was amenable to PCR amplification (Table No. 03, 04 and 05).

Genetic Diversity analysis of Fusarium annulatum using ITS Primer

Genome analysis of *Fusarium annulatum* isolates by ITS primer, in this study has provided evidence

Table 3. Primers Used for PCR amplification

Sr. No.	Name of Primer	Oligo Name	Sequence (5`à 3`)	Tm (°C)	GC- Content ITS Forward
01	ITS Primer	ITS Forward	TCCGTAGGTGAACCTGCGG	57	63.15%
02	ITS Primer	ITS Reverse	TCCTCCGCTTATIGATATGC	53	45%

Table 4. Components of PCR Amplification

Sr. No.	PCR Amplification conditions	Volume
1	DNA	1 ul
2	ITS Forward Primer	2 ul
3	ITS Reverse Primer	2 ul
4	dNTPs (2.5 mM each)	4 ul
5	10X Taq DNA polymerase Assay Buffer	10 ul
6	Taq DNA Polymerase Enzyme (3U/ ml)	1 ul
7	Water	30 ul
8	Total Volume	50 ul

Table 5. Temperature profile used for DNA amplification by ITS Primer

Sr. No.	Steps	Temperature (°C)	Duration	Cycle
1	Initial Denaturation	94	3 Min	
2	Denaturation	94	1 Min	
3	Annealing	50	1 Min	30
4	Primer Extension	72	2 Min	Cycles
5	Final Extension	72	7 Min	
6	Hold	4°C	-	-

Table 6. ITS Primer Used in the Fingerprinting of *Fusarium annulatum* isolates

Sr. No.	Primer	Sequence (5`à 3`)
FOM-1	ITS-1	TCCGTAGGTGAACCTGCGG
FOM-2	ITS-2	CCGTAGGTGAACCTGCGGAG
FOM-3	ITS-3	TATGTTACAGGGTTTGAG
FOM-4	ITS-4	TCCGTAGGTGAACCTGCGG
FOM-5	ITS-5	GTAATGATCCCGTAGGTGAA
FOM-6	ITS-6	ATTGTATGTTACAGGTTTG
FOM-7	ITS-7	CCGTAGGTGAACCTGCGGAG
FOM-8	ITS-8	TCCGTAGGTGAACCTGCGGA

that this Pathogenic fungus varies genetically. This variability should be taken into consideration in different crop. In order to determine the extent of genetic variation of this economically important fungus and relationship with cultural and pathogenic traits. The DNA Fingerprint was generated through ITS primer, based on the DNA sequencing data for each ITS primer for eight isolates

FOM of *Fusarium annulatum*. The Eight isolates of *Fusarium annulatum* were differentiated on the basis of their ITS primer sequence pattern (Table 6). All FOM of *Fusarium annulatum* are indicated existence of genetic variation and high level of genetic variability in the study suggests among selected eight isolates (FOM-01, FOM-02, FOM-03, FOM-04, FOM-05, FOM-06, FOM-07, FOM-08).

Figure 5. Dendrogram demonstrating the relationship among eight FOM isolates of *Fusarium annulatum*

Genetic diversity analysis among eight FOM isolates based on dendrogram generated using ITS Primer.

Dendrogram was constructed on the basis of their variants forms the entire data set of primers assisted identification and analysis of the 08 isolates of *Fusarium annulatum* (Figure 5). The phylogenetic analysis of different FOM of *Fusarium annulatum* shows the evolutionary history, diversification and relationship between different strains. The phylogenetic analysis studies can help the identify the specific *Fusarium annulatum* strains cause the disease in plant and other host. The dendrogram shows genetic variation of these isolates of *Fusarium annulatum* fungi and relationship with cultural and pathogenic traits.

CONCLUSION

Fusarium annulatum has established its importance among the most devastating pathogens all over the world and the research to control it sustainably is still going on. During the present Investigation the pathogenic fungi *Fusarium annulatum* are show the high level Genetic and morphological variability due to difference in geographical and environmental conditions. The ITS primer was used to find out diversity among different isolates of *Fusarium annulatum* at the molecular level characterization. The genetic High-level variability also recorded in Eight FOM of *Fusarium annulatum*. The genetic variation of these isolates of *Fusarium annulatum* fungi and relationship with cultural and pathogenic traits. The *Fusarium annulatum* diversity of this fungus has also

contributed to creating confusion among the taxonomists and it can be more benefit in future once its full potential to explored the *Fusarium annulatum*.

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Conflicts of Interest

Authors declare that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this paper.

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